

Food loss and food waste – the legislative deficit in Germany

José Martínez

Prof. Dr., University of Göttingen (Germany)

Abstract

Food losses arise mainly in connection with production along a value chain. 52 % of food waste in Germany occurs in households. This is caused in particular by the very low food prices in Germany and excessive labelling on the shelf life of food. The German government has set itself the goal of halving food waste by 2030. Existing regulations on waste prevention, recycling and disposal in general are proving inefficient. Due to the largely private origin of food waste, the government is not looking for the solution in law, but in non-binding instruments such as a national strategy and voluntary commitments. Possible options would be food donations from food retailers or the decriminalisation of container diving.

Lebensmittelverluste treten hauptsächlich im Zusammenhang mit der Produktion entlang einer Wertschöpfungskette auf. 52 % der Lebensmittelabfälle in Deutschland fallen in den Haushalten an. Ursache sind insbesondere die sehr niedrigen Lebensmittelpreise in Deutschland und eine übermäßige Kennzeichnung zur Mindesthaltbarkeit von Lebensmitteln. Die deutsche Regierung hat sich das Ziel gesetzt, die Lebensmittelabfälle bis 2030 zu halbieren. Die bestehenden Regelungen zur Abfallvermeidung, zum Recycling und zur Entsorgung im Allgemeinen erweisen sich als ineffizient. Aufgrund des weitestgehend privaten Ursprungs der Lebensmittelverschwendung sucht die Regierung die Lösung nicht im Gesetz, sondern in unverbindlichen Instrumenten wie einer nationalen Strategie und freiwilligen Verpflichtungen. Mögliche Optionen wären Lebensmittelspenden aus dem Lebensmitteleinzelhandel oder die Entkriminalisierung des Containertauchens.

1. Concepts and food waste in figures

First of all, talking about food loss and food waste requires to distinguish between the two concepts. Food losses occur mainly in the context of production along a value chain. They are attributed to technical and infrastructural difficulties. Food waste, on the other hand, refers to food that has been produced for consumption but not consumed or not wanted to be consumed. In addition, a distinction must be made between avoidable, partially avoidable and non-avoidable food waste. The first are those whose consumption would not have been problematic at the time of disposal. Partially avoidable wastes occur due to consumption habits. This second type of food waste should not be disposed of, as is the case with bread crusts or leftover food, for example. The third group, i.e. unavoidable food waste, mainly comprises substances that are unfit for consumption, such as bones.

In Germany, around 12 million tonnes of food waste are generated every year. Per capita, that means that every German wastes about 55 kilos of food per year. 52% of food waste occurs in households, although another study claims that it is only 40%. The second largest contributor to food waste is food processing, with 18%. Gastronomy comes in third place with 14%. Supermarkets dispose of 720,000 tons of food, which is only 4%. If food waste in households were reduced by 50 %, greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in Germany could be reduced by 6 million tonnes of CO₂ equivalent. The value

of (avoidable or partially avoidable) food waste in Germany is estimated at around 21.6 billion euros. However, more than two thirds of the discarded food would still be fit for consumption. In the case of Germany, the composition of food waste is dominated by vegetables (25.4%). This is followed by fruit (17.9%), bakery products (15.1%) and rice (12.4%). Meat and fish, as well as dairy products and beverages, are in single digits.

Food losses can be divided into five areas along the value chain. Starting with harvest losses (about 1 million t), followed by post-harvest losses (about 1.59 million t) and processing losses (about 2.61 million t), i.e. losses that occur in further processing both in industry and at home. In addition, there are distribution losses in the wholesale and retail trade (about 2.575 million t.) and among large consumers (about 3.4 million t.), as well as consumer losses (about 7.2 million t.). facilities such as canteens and restaurants. In the agricultural sector, the harvest and associated losses can be defined as the harvest itself. In the livestock sector, it is the path from breeding to slaughter, but also the extraction of milk and eggs. In crop production, post-harvest losses include all actions of the harvested crop, which can range from the first treatment to transport and storage. In the livestock sector, it includes the spoilage of meat before processing at the slaughterhouse, as well as the spoilage of milk and eggs during transport. Process losses occur during the refining of agricultural raw materials, e.g. cider making or meat processing. Distribution losses originate at the wholesale and retail level, where food is lost, e.g. disposal of a product due to damaged packaging or disposal because a new product design replaces the old one. Consumer losses at the final consumer level are due to poor planning of purchase quantity, poor storage conditions, poor preparation techniques or misinformation about the best-before date, as well as in out-of-home catering.

Why is it mainly private households that dispose of food in Germany? The first reason is the low price of food in Germany. Compared to other industrialised countries, Germany has the lowest food costs. One of the reasons is the long tradition of discount stores, which has flourished since the supermarket chain Aldi entered the food retail sector. Whenever one large discount chain changes its pricing policy, others immediately follow. Another reason is that food has a lower tax rate (7%) than other products (19%).

The second reason is the widespread use of best-before dates in the food sector. There are many areas where it makes sense: for example, fresh meat or milk. But there are just as many areas where it is absurd: for example, salt, sugar or pasta. In Germany, many people believe that best-before dates should be taken seriously and throw these foods away.

2. Legislative deficit

How is the legislator responding to this challenge? The German government has set itself the target of halving food waste by 2030. Germany has a number of regulations for waste prevention, recycling and disposal in general, which partly address the problem of food waste. However, as the persistent amount of food waste shows, these have not been efficient. But the government is not looking for the solution in law, but in non-binding instruments such as a national strategy and voluntary commitments from industry and the food trade. For example, the German Minister of Agriculture does not want to introduce a law against the disposal of perfectly edible food, as France has recently done.

In February 2019, the Federal Cabinet adopted the National Strategy for Reducing Food Waste. The strategy identifies potential causes of food waste. It outlines challenges and areas of activity to substantially reduce food waste along the food supply chain.

The aim is to halve per capita food waste in Germany at retail and consumer level and to reduce food losses along the production and supply chains, including post-harvest losses, by 2030. The Länder, civil society actors and associations from the agri-food sector, artisanal food production and the restaurant and catering sector have been involved in the development of the *National Strategy for Reducing Food Waste*.

Therefore, in our National Strategy, civil society, industry, government and scientists are called upon to contribute to the process necessary to accomplish this task. To this end, participation in sectoral dialogue forums is foreseen: the intention is to work together to develop specific measures on food waste reduction and to set sectoral targets. Dialogue fora have been set up for primary production, processing, wholesale, retail, out-of-home catering and households.

In March 2020, the Federal Minister for Food, together with the presidents of seven associations from the agri-food sector, trade, artisanal food production and the restaurant and catering sector, signed a general agreement on reducing food waste. This general agreement forms the basis for co-operation in the implementation of the *National Strategy for the Reduction of Food Waste*.

Germany launches many **communication campaigns** that can be divided into governmental and private campaigns (launched by universities, NGOs, activists). In particular, a network on food waste prevention has been created, which aims to bring together various stakeholders from the fields of research and consumer protection to conduct and report on research on food waste issues. BMEL launched the "Too Good for Waste!" initiative in March 2012. The main character is a potato - of course, we are in Germany. This campaign has focused public attention on the issue of food waste and made consumers have a greater appreciation for food. *Too Good for Waste!* is continually being expanded and extended to include the entire food supply chain.

How successful are these measures? With regard to Delegated Decision (EU) 2019/1597, which requires in-depth measurements at four-year intervals for each sector of the value chain, reliable data to determine the quantities of food waste in Germany on a statistically representative basis are still lacking. The overall potential for food waste reduction in Germany is approximately 11.9 million tonnes, of which 6.6 million tonnes are theoretically avoidable or still fit for consumption. Most of the avoidable food waste is from households. In contrast to the UK, for example, household food waste in Germany has remained at more or less the same level since 2012. Given these results, the question arises whether awareness campaigns and initiatives in Germany will have a similar positive effect as in other countries. Therefore, the potential impact of consumer-related measures in Germany requires further research, especially the feasibility of achieving the policy objectives. However, the results of recent studies do not show a statistically relevant reduction of food waste along the different sectors of the food value chain.

3. Possible options

• 3.1. Food donations from the food retail trade

One possible solution to food waste would be to offer German retailers simplified options for donating food that is still edible and fit for consumption. The draft federal law to simplify food donations must be in accordance with the German Basic Law (LF). According to Art. 72 para. 1 and Art. 74 para. 1 no. 20 alternative 1 FG, the federal government has concurrent legislative competence for the "law on foodstuffs, including the animals used for their production". On this basis, a national law on food donations could be formulated. According to Art. 72 para. 2 LF the Federal Government is only entitled to legislate "if and insofar as the creation of equivalent living conditions or the maintenance of legal or economic unity in the federal territory requires federal legislation". This means that the Federation must achieve the listed objective better than the Länder with legislation. However, the Federation only acquires the power to regulate "when living conditions in the Länder have diverged significantly in a way that is detrimental to the federal social structure or such a development becomes concretely evident". Moreover, the legislation of the federal government must also maintain the functioning of the economic area of the Federal Republic of Germany. Consequently, the interest of the entire state can only be justified if (or if not) regulations are made at the state level that negatively affect the entire economy. As far as the federal legislative competence for food donations is concerned, it could be argued that as soon as different regulations on food donations are established at the state level, divergent living conditions can be expected, as individuals will have different opportunities to obtain free access to food. This would lead to a change in the social sphere. In addition to the economic component, it should be added that the top 5 food retailers have a total market power of 67.9% in Germany. The centrally organised food retail sector would be weakened if it had to follow different regulations on the distribution of donations at state level.

3.2. Decriminalisation of dumpster diving

Dumpster diving is considered theft in Germany and is still illegal. However, the courts are very inconsistent in their prosecution of this crime. If one looks at this problem from a legal point of view, the accusation of criminal behaviour is quite legitimate. At first glance, it appears that the owner gives up ownership of the food by disposing of it. However, there are several reasons why supermarket operators do not want to dispose of waste until it is collected. For example, it can be assumed that most supermarket operators do not want to give away older food, as this could affect their sales revenue. Also, securing the containers with padlocks makes it clear that ownership will not be relinquished. Containers with leftover food in supermarkets are always locked separately, also for reasons of civil liability. Therefore, theft according to § 242 of the German Criminal Code is certainly a possibility. If the containers are opened, the offender is formally liable for a particularly serious case of theft (§§ 242, 243 StGB) and property damage (§ 303 StGB).

Finally, from the point of view of legal policy, it has to be mentioned that urban collection may be punishable, but does not deserve punishment. This is also recognised by criminal prosecutors, who make generous use of their possibility to discontinue such proceedings according to the Code of Criminal Procedure (cf. LG Aachen, ref. 94 Ns 15/13). In case of discontinuance, no penalty is imposed.

At the political level, there are calls for the public prosecutor's office to receive "a general instruction that the policy against food waste must be on a par with the actions of the public prosecutor's office".

In this respect, closer cooperation with social organisations is necessary. He also rightly calls for society to rethink these issues, which ultimately affect us all.

4. Conclusion

Therefore, we can conclude: The German government does not use all means to reduce food waste. Two important instruments remain untouched to this day for political reasons: 1. the increase of food prices by raising the food tax. 2. the ban on the use of best-before dates for products that cannot expire biologically.

Bibliography

Archiv von Bundesregierung.de: Lebensmittelspenden an Tafeln sind umsatzfrei, 2012. <https://archiv.bundesregierung.de/archiv-de/lebensmittelspenden-an-tafeln-sind-umsatzsteuerfrei-423778>

Ausmaß und Umwelteffekte der Lebensmittelverschwendung in Deutschland, 2015. https://www.wwf.de/fileadmin/fm-wwf/Publikationen-PDF/WWF_Studie_Das_grosse_Wegschmeissen.pdf

Azzurro Paolo/Gaiani Silvia/Vittuari Matteo (FUSIONS): Italy - Country report on national food waste policy, 2016. <https://www.eu-fusions.org/phocadownload/country-report/FUSIONS%20IT%20Country%20Report%2030.06.pdf>

Bio by Deloitte, Europäischer Wirtschafts- und Sozialausschluss: Vergleichende Studie Gesetzliche Bestimmungen und die Verfahren der EU-Mitgliedstaaten bezüglich Lebensmittelspenden - Zusammenfassung, 2014. <https://www.eesc.europa.eu/resources/docs/qe-05-14-069-de-n.pdf>

Bundesministerium für Ernährung und Landwirtschaft: Das Menschenrecht auf Nahrung verwirklichen, 2015. https://www.bmel.de/DE/Landwirtschaft/Welternahrung/_Texte/MenschenrechtAufNahrung.html

Bundesministerium für Ernährung und Landwirtschaft: Ermittlung der Mengen weggeworfener Lebensmittel und Hauptursachen für die Entstehung von Lebensmittelabfällen in Deutschland Zusammenfassung einer Studie der Universität Stuttgart, 2012. https://www.bmel.de/SharedDocs/Downloads/Ernaehrung/WvL/Studie_Lebensmittel_abfaelle_Faktenblatt.pdf?blob=publicationFile

Bundesministerium für Ernährung und Landwirtschaft: Initiative "Zu gut für die Tonne", 2018. https://www.bmel.de/DE/Ernaehrung/ZuGutFuerDieTonne/zgfdt_node.html

Bundesministerium für Ernährung und Landwirtschaft: Leitfaden für die Weitergabe von Lebensmitteln an soziale Einrichtungen - Rechtliche Aspekte, 2018. http://www.bmel.de/SharedDocs/Downloads/Broschueren/LeifadenWeitergabeLMS_ozEinrichtungen.pdf?blob=

Bundesministerium für wirtschaftliche Zusammenarbeit und Entwicklung: Die globalen Ziele für nachhaltige Entwicklung - Ziel 12 Für nachhaltige Konsum- und Produktionsmuster sorgen, 2018. https://www.bmz.de/de/ministerium/ziele/2030_agenda/17_ziele/ziel_012_konsum/index.html

Bundesministerium für wirtschaftliche Zusammenarbeit und Entwicklung: Internationale Ziele - Die Agenda 2030 für nachhaltige Entwicklung, 2018. https://www.bmz.de/de/ministerium/ziele/2030_agenda/index.html

BVerfG of August 05, 2020 (2 BvR 1985/19, 2 BvR 1986/19) - Zur Verfassungsmäßigkeit der Strafbarkeit des sogenannten Containerns als Diebstahl

Deutscher Bundestag: Wissenschaftliche Dienste Ausarbeitung - Rechtliche Vorgaben in Frankreich gegen Lebensmittelverschwendung. WD 5-3000-095/18, 2018. <https://www.bundestag.de/blob/568808/21ec9f0fbd1bce3c48c063f24498428e/wd-5-095-18-pdf-data.pdf>

Esser Robert/Scharnberg Josephine: Anfängerklausur - Strafrecht: Containern, JuS (Juristische Schulung) 2012, S. 809-814

EU-FUSIONS: EU-Fusions, 2018. <https://www.eu-fusions.org/>

EU-Projekt zur Reduzierung von Lebensmittelabfällen gestartet, 2018. <https://eu-refresh.org/refresh-eu-projekt-zur-reduzierung-von-lebensmittelabf%C3%A4llen-gestartet>

FAO, IFAD, UNICEF, WFP and WHO: The State of Food Security and Nutrition in the World 2018 - Building climate resilience for food security and nutrition, 2018. <http://www.fao.org/3/I9553EN/i9553en.pdf>

FAO: Global Food losses and food waste - extent, causes and prevention, 2011. <http://www.fao.org/docrep/014/mb060e/mb060e00.pdf>

Fischer Thomas: Kommentar zum Strafgesetzbuch, 65. Auflage, 2018

GfK: Systematic assessment of the impact of food waste on private households in Germany - a key study report. Durchgeführt für das Bundesministerium für Ernährung und Landwirtschaft, 2017. https://www.zugutfuertietonne.de/fileadmin/Neuigkeiten/PDF-Dateien/Studie_GfKBMEI.pdf

Hellermann Carolin/Birkholz Marco: Containern - eine sachenrechtliche Herausforderung, Jura 2020, S. 303-313

Hoffmeister Friederike/Margraf Rainer/Noack, Eva Marie: Lebensmittelverwertung erwünscht, doch Containern verboten?, Jahrbuch der Österreichischen Gesellschaft für Agrarökonomie, Band 24, 2014, S. 255-264

Ipsen Jörn: Staatsrecht I - Staatsorganisationsrecht, 30. Auflage, 2018.

ISWA: Ermittlung der weggeworfenen Lebensmittelmengen und Vorschläge zur Verminderung der Wegwerfrate bei Lebensmitteln in Deutschland, 2012. https://www.bmel.de/SharedDocs/Downloads/Ernaehrung/WvL/Studie_Lebensmittel_abfaelle_Langfassung.pdf?blob=publicationFile

Joecks Wolfgang/Miebach Klaus: Münchener Kommentar zum Strafgesetzbuch, 3. Auflage, 2017

Kämmerer Jörn Axel: Staatsorganisationsrecht, 2. Auflage, 2011

Kindhäuser Urs/Neumann Ulfrid/Paeffgen Hans-Ulrich: Kommentar zum Strafgesetzbuch, Band 1, 5. Auflage, 2017

Lackner Karl/Kühl Kristian: Kommentar zum Strafgesetzbuch, 28. Auflage, 2014.

Lebensmittelzeitung Retailytics: Top 30 Lebensmittelhandel Deutschland, 2017, <https://www.dfv.de/media/media/1/Top-30-Lebensmittelhandel-2017-4129.pdf>

Leverenz Dominik/Schneider Felicitas/Schmidt Thomas/Hafner Gerold/Nevárez Zuemmy/Kranert Martin: Food Waste Generation in Germany in the Scope of European Legal Requirements for Monitoring and Reporting. Sustainability 2021, 13, 6616. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13126616>

Meyer Alfred Hagen/Streinzig Rudolf: Kommentar zum LFGB, BasisVO, HCVO Lebensmittel- und Futtermittelgesetzbuch, Basis-Verordnung (EG) Nr. 178/2002, Health Claim VO 1924/2006, 2. Auflage 2012

Ministerium für Umwelt, Landwirtschaft, Natur- und Verbraucherschutz des Landes Nordrhein-Westfalen: Was tun gegen Lebensmittelverschwendung? Ideen und Anregungen für eine neue Wertschätzungskultur, 2017. https://www.umwelt.nrw.de/fileadmin/redaktion/Broschueren/lebensmittelverschwendung_bf.pdf

Müller Lisa Marie: Lebensmittelverschwendung als Herausforderung für das europäische Abfallrecht, EurUP 2017, S. 84-92

Noack Eva-Maria/Rovers Anja-Karolina/Kühling Lena/Marggraf Rainer: Was Menschen bewegt, Lebensmittel aus dem Müll zu holen; eine explorative Studie zum Containern. In: Britz Wolfgang et al. (Hrsg): Agrar- und Ernährungswirtschaft: Regional vernetzt und global erfolgreich: 56. Jahrestagung der Gesellschaft für Wirtschafts- und Sozialwissenschaften des Landbaues e.V. vom 28. bis 30. September 2016, S. 125-136

Rengier Rudolf: Strafrecht Allgemeiner Teil, 8. Auflage, 2016

Rennicke Jan: Zur strafrechtlichen Behandlung des Containerns de lege lata und de lege ferenda, ZIS 2020, S. 343-348

Sachs Michael: Kommentar zum Grundgesetz, 8. Auflage 2018

Säcker Franz-Jürgen/Rixecker Roland/Oetker Hartmut/Limberg Bettina: Münchener Kommentar zum Bürgerlichen Gesetzbuch, 7. Auflage, 2017

Schmidt Thomas: Lebensmittel im Müll Ist es möglich, die Lebensmittelverluste bis 2030 zu halbieren? In: Wissenschaft erleben, Thünen 01/2018. https://refowas.de/images/wissenschaft_erleben_2018-1.pdf

Schönke Adolf/Schröder Horst: Kommentar zum Strafgesetzbuch, 29. Auflage, 2014

Stenmarck Åsa/Hanssen Ole Jörgen/Silvennoinen Kirsi/Katajajuuri Juha-Matti/Werge Mads: Initiatives on prevention of food waste in the retail and wholesale trades. VL report B1988, Stockholm: Swedish Environmental Research Institute, 2011

Streinz Rudolf: Kommentar zum EUV/AEUV - Vertrag über die Europäische Union, Vertrag über die Arbeitsweise der Europäischen Union, Charta der Grundrechte der Europäischen Union EUV/AEUV, 3. Auflage, 2018

Umweltbundesamt: Daten zur Umwelt - Umwelt, Haushalte und Konsum, 2015. https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/sites/default/files/medien/378/publikationen/daten/zur_umwelt_umwelt_haushalte_und_konsum_2.pdf

Voit Wolfgang/Grube, Markus: Lebensmittelinformationsverordnung - LMIV, 2. Auflage, 2016

Wessels Johannes/Beulke Werner/Satzger Helmut: Strafr AT, 43. Auflage, 2013

WWF Deutschland: Das grosse Wegschmeissen. Vom Acker bis zum Verbraucher: Ausmaß und Umwelteffekte der Lebensmittelverschwendung in Deutschland. <https://www.wwf.de/themen-projekte/landwirtschaft/ernaehrung-konsum/lebensmittelverschwendung/das-grosse-wegschmeissen>

Zentrum für europäischen Verbraucherschutz: Lebensmittelverschwendung in Frankreich, 2018. <https://www.cec-zev.eu/de/themen/alltag-in-frankreich/lebensmittelverschwendung-in-frankreich>

Zipfel Walter/Rathke Kurt-Dietrich/Sosnitza Olaf: Kommentar zum Lebensmittelrecht, 170. EL, März 2018